

USE OF MODIS IMAGERY TO GENERATE A HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF WILDLAND FIRE REGIME IN SOUTHERN PART OF GEDAREF STATE - SUDAN

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Abstract: This study was carried out in Southern part of Gedaref state where there are important localities for the state and Sudan .It portrays different land cover and land use types including agriculture, forests and range land. This study was directed towards the feasibility of using remote sensing and geographic information systems (GIS) through MODIS data to document the history of fire and produce maps of burned areas in southern part of Gedaref state for season (2000-2001) to (2012-2013) in order to understand fire regime in the area and hence contribute in improvement of fire management program. The methodology applied in order to achieve this goal is an analysis of the images obtained by the MODIS sensor to set the burned areas. Collective of 27 Images on every season is processed (351 image for 13 seasons) and analyzed to extract the burned area using MODIS images) each season (from 30th August to the first of April, the next year). ENVI 4.7 and ARCMAP 9.3 software's were used for image processing and maps production. The study revealed that the fire season which is usually starts with beginning of the dry season in the mid of September and continue until the ends of the April with the peak of burned areas in November and February. The study also shows that there is two peaks of burnt area within the fire seasons this is appear in the season of 2000-20001 and the season of 2008-2009. The study indicates that wild land fires occur annually over large areas. There are clear absent of previous studies and historical field data in the study area to carry the validation upon it. The frequency map shows that the higher frequency burned area is located in the southern and east part of the study

area and the least frequency burned area is located in the north part of the study while the medium frequency burned area dominated in the middle part of the study area.

Key words: FIRE REGIME, MODIS IMAGERY and frequency map.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Gadaref is one of the 18 states of Sudan. It has an area of (75263 km²) and the total. Population of the state is estimated 1,348,378 people, annual growth rate 3.7%, and 25% urban 73.7% rural, 1.3% nomadic. Fire is an important and widely used tool to meet land management goals and maintain the functioning of ecological processes. However, every year wildfires destroy large area of forest, woodland and other vegetation, causing loss of many human and animal lives and immense economic damage. There are also impacts on society and the environment –for example, damage of human health, loss of biological diversity, release of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases, damage of recreational and amenity values and much more [1]. The fire regime is an objective measurement of fire's historic natural occurrence in the landscape, which is not necessarily the current condition or appearance.

The fire regime includes the season, frequency, intensity, and spatial distribution of fires. There is quite a wide variability of "natural" intervals, intensities, and seasons, but some generalities

can be made. Each vegetation type has its own fire regime. A standardized set of five fire regimes is used nationwide [2] [3]

The systems are used for the characterization of turbulence-scale spatial and temporal Patterns of disturbance and subsequent response and restore ecosystems [4]. Integration disorder attributes including type, the frequency and severity, duration, and extent [5]. Classifications of fire regimes can be based on the characteristics of the fire itself or the fire effects Produced by Fire. [6]. The positive and negative roles of fire must be recognized, as well as the need for holistic management rather than just suppression. Despite the severe social, economic and environmental impacts of fires, reliable current information on extent and causes impact and costs is insufficient .Yet such information essential to the development of policies, legislation and plan for prevention and suppression [1]. Although southern part of Gedaref State suffering from wildland fire, but there is lack of information and the fire regime is not investigated yet. The dry season start two to three weeks after rainy season in September to May/June and the fire danger increase with grass dry out and the existence of human activities[7].There is no specialized fire management organization, but there is annual program to build fire lines, but usually faced with shortage of budget availability . So this study was aimed to produce maps of burned areas for the Southern part of Gadaref state from 2000-2012 to document the history of fire (wildfire extend, frequency and seasonality) using MODIS satellite data.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Methodology of the burned area mapping

This study was directed towards using remote sensing and geographic information systems (GIS) through MODIS data to document the history of fire and produce maps of burned areas in southern part of Gadaref state for season (2000-2001) to (2012-2013) and using ENVI software 4.7 and Arc map software 9.3 in order to processing image in computer. It based on the methodology applied in order to achieve this goal on an analysis of the images obtained by the MODIS sensor to set the burned areas. Collective of 27 files on every season was processed (351 image for 13 seasons) and analyzed to extract the burned area. The following steps are carried out:

Data Images acquisition

Images acquisition of MODIS, 8 days surface reflectance product 250 m spatial resolution are Ordered and freely downloaded for each season (from August 28 to April first, next year).

Study Area Subset

The study area was subset in order to include Elrahd, West Galabat, East Galabat. and Elfashqa localities. Shape file has been prepared for the study area using Arc GIS 9.3 software, uses the same shape file to subset out the original images using ENVI 4.7 software, and the typical subset frame of the same area was saved then used for sub setting rest of the images.

NDVI Calculation

With ENVI band math facilities Normalized Difference vegetation Index (NDVI) was computed for all the images by applying the following formula NDVI:

$$[\text{Float (B2) -float (B1)}] / [\text{float (B2) + float (B1)}]$$

Where:

B1 = Band1 (Red)

B2 = Band2 (Near infrared)

NDVI is based on the reflection characteristics of vegetation which gives increase in reflection from red over infrared for the healthy vegetation due to the presences of green chlorophyll and the internal construction of plants, the fact that burned vegetation looks black due to the absence of green chlorophyll gives the NDVI the privilege to detect the burned area as pixels can be classified into ranges of burned scares area that takes the lowest NDVI value (NDVI values range from 1to -1) [9].

Change detection generation

In order to detect the burned areas within 8 days each previous NDVI image was subtracted from earlier ones and, hence Change was detected, this procedures were carried out for all images in the investigated seasons.

Density slicing

Color density slide was created by selecting pixels of the lowest change detection value and the one with the highest value within the burned area

Region of Interest Generation and Mask Building

Region of interest covering the real burned area is used to build mask in order to eliminate noise, which look like burned area for example harvested crop field.

Regions of interest are created for each change detection image in order to mask out noises. Then unburned areas that contain values of NDVI variation similar to that of burned areas are removed (masked out) to create a new noise free image. In order To eliminate overlap occurred during burned area mapping, each pixel having DN more than one in the final image is rendered to one. Band math of ENVI software is used to remove the double or more burned area mapping.

Monthly Burned Area Image Generation

The image was created monthly burned area each season by collecting all the burned areas detected between all successive images in the same month.

Total Burned Area Image Generation

The total burned area image was generated by using ENVI to add all burned areas detected among all successive images in the same season. This was done for each season.

Raster to Vector

Resulting monthly total burned area images were transferred from raster to vector (shape file) for use in ARC GIS software 9.3 to calculate all the burned area polygons and facilitate the preparation of the final burned area maps

Calculating Burned Area Polygons and Maps Production

The monthly and the total burned area maps in southern part of Gadaref state for the season (2000-2001) to (2012-2013) are produced using Arc GIS 9.3 software

Generating burned area frequency map

To perform this task all the burned area maps of each season are summed in order to produce one image of which each pixel DN represent the number of times burned.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

One of the main causes and spread of forest fires is the biomass accumulation both on the forest floor and in abandoned agricultural lands and pastures [10]. Weather conditions have a catalytic effect, as fires propagate more easily in a hot and dry environment. Two factors were influence the extent of burned area every year, the total amount of rainfall and the extent of burned area in the previous year. High rainfall increases the development of grasses, which considered as the main fuel available for fire. Fire reduces seed bank inside the burned area so the amount of grasses are expected to be lesser in the years where burned area was at large extend in the previous year.

Table 1: The starting and ends date with the total burnt area for each season

Season	Start Date	End Date	Burnt Area km ²
2000-2001	21.Sep.2000	23.Apr.2001	2383.27
2001-2002	6.Sep.2001	30.Mar.2002	1751.26
2002-2003	14.Sep.2002	23.Apr.2003	1781.97
2003-2004	14.Sep.3003	22.Apr.2004	1601.57
2004-2005	13.Sep.2004	23.Apr.2005	1533.40
2005-2006	14.Sep.2005	23.Apr.2006	2012.81
2006-2007	14.Sep.2006	23.Apr.2007	1865.44
2007-2008	14.Sep.2007	6.Apr.2008	1874.41
2008-2009	21.sep.2008	23.Apr.2009	2910.27
2009-2010	14.Sep.2009	23.Apr.2010	1904.67
2010-2011	14.Sep.2010	30.Apr.2011	1342.68
2011-2012	13.Sep.2011	30.Apr.2012	820.18
2012-2013	21.Sep.2012	30.Apr.2013	1478.99

The analysis of the fire information over the period 2000 to 2012 resulted in an investigation of the fire regime in the study area. The fire season starts few weeks after rainy season and usually extend from September to April (table 1), because the remaining high biomass of vegetation is senescent and the weather extremely dry. During that period large uncontrolled wild fires can be very devastating. The spatial and temporal distribution is generally

variable. The study indicated this variability and clearly indicates peak fire activity in November and February during the year 2000-2012 as shown in figure (1). The study also shows that there is two peaks of burnt area within the fire seasons this is appear in the season of 2000-20001 and the season of 2008-2009 due to the high rainfall in these years, which increased the fuel loads (Figure 2).

The Slash and burn agriculture that is practiced in the South-East of the study area, causes an increase in fire activity at the end of the dry season in February, which concur with the preparation of the fields for the next crop season. Also the peak fire activity in November due to existence high biomass of vegetation is senescent and weather very dry. Comparing between the centre, south, south-East and middle and north part of study area we found that, see (Table 2 and fig 3).

Most of the fire activity takes place in study area, because the possibility of their continuous herbaceous cover combined with human

activities such as honey and gum collection, hunting and charcoal production. In the north and north- west of the study area the lower biomass maybe is usually used by the cattle and fire activity is consequently very low, also this area was mechanized farmed.

The fire season start in about month later just after the ends of the rainy season in the mid of September where the grass start to drier and continue up to the ends of April. Surface vegetation, especially grasses may dry very quickly after the end of the rainy season and the fire break program was not completed [7].

Fig. 1: Burned area during 2000-2012/month

Fig. 2: Total Burned area 2000-2012/year

Table (2): The percentage of total burnt area to the total area in each season

Season	Burned Area km ²	Percentage%
2000-2001	2383.27	13.45
2001-2002	1751.26	9.89
2002-2003	1781.97	10.06
2003-3004	1601.57	9.04
2004-2005	15334.0	8.66
2005-2006	2012.81	11.36
2006-2007	1865.44	10.53
2007-2008	1874.41	10.58
2008-2009	2910.27	16.43
2009-2010	1904.67	10.75
2010-2011	1342.68	7.58
2011-2012	820.18	4.63
2012-2013	1478.99	8.35

Total Area: 17716.34 Km²

Table 3: Total Burned Area during 2000-2012/Month/ km²

No	SEASON	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	TOTAL
1	2000-2001	18	208.5	412.1	496.8	330.6	482.1	355.7	78.7	2383.3
2	2001-2002	37.2	39.5	293.3	306.4	461.0	381.4	235.5		1751.3
3	2002-2003	24.9	179.5	310.5	193.9	301.5	435.4	203.8	132.4	1781.9
4	2003-2004	22.4	29.1	321.2	282.1	222.1	391.3	189.2	142.1	1601.5
5	2004-2005	7.6	123.9	415.2	302.8	182.4	313.7	121.6	66.2	1533.4
6	2005-2006	40.7	91.3	543.4	185.7	263.0	329.5	287.6	271.6	2012.8
7	2006-2007	48.7	101.1	343.0	185.5	304.2	354.3	325.1	203.5	1865.4
8	2007-2008	31.2	99.3	371.3	314.6	215.3	363.4	479.3		1874.4
9	2008-2009	40.0	211.3	413.1	401.0	219.2	508.1	513.4	519.1	2910.3
10	2009-2010	35.1	147.1	389.3	249.0	211.4	439.3	313.2	120.3	1904.7
11	2010-2011	23.4	81.1	200.6	271.6	152.2	224.4	233.8	154.7	1342.7
12	2011-2012	33.3	41.0	71.1	112.6	242.3	165.1	73.5		820.2
13	2012-2013	40.7	133.2	295.7	303.3	50.8	238.6	221.4	194.3	1479.0
	Total	403.2	1444.9	4370.1	3605.3	3160.0	4124.3	3553.1	1882.9	

Table (4) show the total burnt area and percentage per fire frequency or number of times burnt. Figure (3) Diagram shows the fire frequency compare to the total area. It is clear from the frequency map that the higher frequency burnt area was located in the southern

, southern east and southern west part of the study area and the least frequency burnt area was located in the north part of the study whereas the medium frequency burnt area located in the middle part of the study area.

Table (4) Total burnt area and percentage per fire frequency

Frequency	Burnt Area km ²	Percentage%
1-3 times	6638.5	37.5
4-6 times	1984	11.2
7-9 times	398.8	2.3
10-13 times	31.7	.18

Fig. 4: Diagram shows the fire frequency compare to the total area

Forest is predicted to retreat owing to climate change [11], [12] and land-use practices [13], [14], which may also facilitate grass invasion and increase both the frequencies and intensities of wildfires. The rate of grass invasion was low during the first years of the fire but then will increase substantially, particularly after the high-intensity fires [15]. Fire intensity generally increased with fine fuel loads, fires were more intense where grasses were more abundant, especially along forest edges. After episodes of intense and frequent fires that exceed forest resilience, recovery may require many fire-free decades. It seems more likely that many fire-disturbed forests will permanently transition into grassy ecosystems.

Repeated and severe fires not only alter forest structure and microclimate in ways that facilitate grass invasion and establishment, but also reduce the competitiveness of the native woody vegetation; fires (i) kill seed trees [16], (ii) increase seed predation of native tree species [16], (iii) lower seed germination [17] and (iv) reduce tree seedling density and diversity [18]. Despite these insights, the question of how much disturbance is too much to cause a change in the state of this system is still hard to answer. Empirical evidence suggests that instead of grass domination, fire-degraded forests may become dominated by vines, re-sprouts and pioneer tree species. While the presence of grasses is expected to be transient and strongly associated with high fire frequencies [5].

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

Wildfires are largely extent in some parts of the study area during the period of the study 2000-2012. The fire season starts usually in middle of September and lasted towards the ends of April. Burned area is occur in the southern and middle parts of the study area, while rarely are burned in the northern part. Since it concurs with the fires, there is evidence that land cleaning for agriculture and charcoal making are playing role behind fire outbreak. MODIS images used for burned area mapping proved to be efficient.

It is clear from the frequency map that the higher frequency burned area is located in the southern and east part of the study area and the least frequency burned area is located in the north part of the study whereas the medium frequency burned area located in the middle part of the study area.

The following issues should considered for more investigation

- The various causes of wildfire.
- The social impacts of wildfire.
- The positive and negative impacts of wildfire on flora and fauna.
- The relation between dispute and outbreak of fire in the study.
- The noise caused by non burned areas that have the same change detection value as in the burned areas.
- Development of integrated fire management plan.

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